

Kinetics of Substitution of 2,4,6-Trichloropyrimidine : Enhanced Reactivity of 2-Chloro Position[#]

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Chapman *et al.*¹ in their extensive work on nucleophilic displacement reactions have made important observations about the reactivity of 4-chloro and 2-chloro substituents in pyrimidine. They observed that the 4-chloro substituent is highly reactive compared to chlorine at position-2. Later they postulated² that in purine system the order of reactivity is 8-chloro > 6-chloro > 2-chloro substituents. This suggests that the reactivity of 2-chlorine flanked by two heterocyclic nitrogens is dependent upon the particular system.

Results and Discussion

We have studied the kinetics of nucleophilic substitution of 2,4,6-trichloropyrimidine with NaOH, Na₂CO₃, NaHCO₃-Na₂CO₃, NaHCO₃ and a few aliphatic and aromatic bases in 30% aqueous alcohol, 30% aqueous acetone, 30% dimethyl sulphoxide and 30% aqueous acetonitrile and recorded some interesting observations regarding the relative activity of 2, 4 and 6 halogen substituents in the system.

The reaction has been found to be second order : first order with respect to 2,4,6-trichloropyrimidine and first order with respect to the substituting agent. The second order rate constants have been computed by the modified Chapman's equation,

$$k_2 = \frac{2.303}{t(a-2b)} \log \frac{b(a-2x)}{a(b-x)}$$

A typical run is given below which clearly

establishes that there is no autocatalysis observed in these reactions with the above solvent systems. The values of rate constants are given in Table 1. There is no solvolysis in the solvents except in DMSO where due correction has been applied to solvolysis if any, in any case not exceeding 5%. The second order rate constant values are given in Tables 2 and 3 at 40°.

TABLE 1

TCP = C.002178 M, amline = 0.01049 M, acetone water = 30:70, Temp = 40°

Reaction %	t s	(a-2x)	(b-x)	k ² × 10 ² dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
10	360	0.010 053 4	0 001 960 2	2.6
20	888	0.009 817 8	0 001 742 4	2.5
30	1 350	0.009 18 2 2	0 001 524 6	2.7
40	1 992	0.008 746 6	0 001 306 8	2.7
50	2 688	0.008 311 0	0.001 089 0	2.8
60	3 720	0.007 874 0	0 000 871 2	2.7
				Avg. 2.67

TABLE 2

Substrate	Substituting agent	Solvent	k ₂ × 10 ² dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
2,4,6-Trichloro pyrimidine	NaOH		Very fast in all the solvent mixtures studied
	NaHCO ₃ -Na ₂ CO ₃	30% Aq alcohol	2.37
		30% Aq acetone	0.19
	Na ₂ CO ₃	30% Aq alcohol	Fast
		30% Aq acetone	2.44
	NaHCO ₃	30% Aq alcohol	0.07
30% Aq acetone		0.02	

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TABLE 3

Substrate: 2,4,6-trichloropyrimidine Substituting agent	$k_2 \times 10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$			
	30% aq. alcohol	30% aq. DMSO	30% aq. acetone	30% aq. acetonitrile
Methylamine	87.51	71.10	50.30	61.20
Diethylamine	73.95	43.88	46.14	45.00
Benzylamine	17.70	20.75	8.79	8.49
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	10.40	5.76	6.26	3.70
Aniline	4.62	3.35	2.45	1.64
<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	1.65	0.85	0.97	0.45

The following facts emerge from the experimental data. (i) The stoichiometry has been found to be 1:2 which is effectively 1:1 as one mole of the base is used up by the side-reaction of hydrochloride formation necessitating the use of Chapman's modified equation for the reaction with primary and secondary bases. (ii) This suggests that only 2-chloro substituent is hydrolysed and not 4- and 6-chloro substituents. This is further confirmed by 1:1 stoichiometry observed with NaOH where there is no accompanying side-reaction. The stoichiometry continues to be 1:1 in all other buffer systems, like carbonate and bicarbonate systems. It is clear that 4- and 6-halogens are similarly situated in the ring both being *ortho* to each nitrogen. Hence, they should be displaced with excess alkali leading to 4,6-dihydroxy-2-chloropyrimidine with stoichiometry 1:2. In the extreme cases the stoichiometry will be 1:3 with the formation of 2,4,6-trihydroxypyrimidine. But the observed stoichiometry 1:1 rules out the above two possibilities leading one to conclude that it is the 2-chloro halogen that is being displaced. This amply establishes that only one halogen is being displaced and that is the 2-chloro substituent and not 4-chloro or 6-chloro substituent as they are structurally similar in which case we should have observed 1:2 stoichiometry in alkali. The reactions have been conducted with 1:5 stoichiometry and even after 48 h the stoichiometry continues to be 1:1 with alkali, which confirms that it is a single displacement process of 2-chloro substituent under these conditions. (iii) The reaction rate has been found to be very fast with piperidine in all the solvent systems studied. The observed order of reactivity with primary and secondary bases under these conditions has been found to

be piperidine > methylamine > benzylamine > *p*-toluidine > aniline > *p*-chloroaniline, which is quite in order with the electronic theory of substituent effects and corresponding basicity. (iv) Dimethylaniline is very sluggish in its reactivity with 2,4,6-trichloropyrimidine indicating that the steric hindrance is dominant eclipsing the basicity factor. (v) The solvent effect appears to be of the general order alcohol > aq. DMSO > aq. acetone > aq. acetonitrile. The reversal of the rates in a few cases may be due to factors like solvation, acidic or basic nature of the solvent, non-random distribution of the components of the mixed solvent and effect of solvent on molecular dispersion. (vi) A novel behaviour has been observed in reaction with pyridine. Reactions occur till the displacement of all the halogens in the system in a facile manner. The stoichiometry is 1:3 unlike with primary and secondary bases. The second order rate constants for the three consecutive displacements are: $k_1 = 0.0072 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_2 = 0.0057 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k_3 = 0.0032 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Chart 1

These have been obtained by Svirbely's analysis³ The obvious reason for these reactions to occur in this system or in other words the displacement of all the halogens, is the formation of the first product 4,6-dichloro-2-pyrimidyl-pyridinium cation which has an enormous electron-withdrawing power leading to the substitution of the other two halogens. This situation does not prevail with primary and secondary bases or hydroxylic agents as the first in these cases does not have a cationic group as it is either a hydroxy derivative or a substituted secondary or tertiary compound with liberation of HCl. The product has been found to be 2,4,6-pyrimidyl-tripyrindiniumtrichloride, the hydrolysis of which has been checked for acid if any and has been found to be negligible. The stoichiometry equations are given in Chart 1.

Experimental

2,4,6-Trichloropyrimidine (Fluka, b.p. 214–16°) was used. All other chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade.

Reaction kinetics were followed by estimating the liberated halide argentometrically. Rates were followed at least upto 70% of the reaction and the results were found to be reproducible within $\pm 3\%$ error.

References

1. N. B. CHAPMAN and C. W. REES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 1190; N. B. CHAPMAN and D. Q. RUSSELL-HILL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 1563.
2. N. B. CHAPMAN and G. B. BARLIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 3017.
3. W. J. SVIRBELY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 255.

